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Novi Sad, Serbia**

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EXPOSURE OF PATIENTS TO SODIUM FROM EFFERVESCENT DOSAGE FORMS

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Sodium in form of sodium salts is often used as an excipient in order to increase product solubility. Effervescent dosage forms contain sodium bicarbonate and sodium carbonate which with acidic agents in water produce carbon dioxide. Effervescent and soluble dosage forms contain high levels of sodium salts. Long-term increase of sodium intake can lead to increased blood pressure across all age ranges.

Data about sodium levels in effervescent dosage forms was obtained from Summary of Product Characteristics from website of Medicines and Medical Devices Agency of Serbia (MMDAS). Data about Recommended Dietary Allowance and Adequate Intake of sodium was obtained from official website of Food and Nutrition Board, Institute of Medicine, National Academies. Maximum daily doses recommended by the manufacturer and approved by MMDAS were observed. Average exposure to sodium through consumption of maximum daily doses for each age group was calculated as percentages of the adequate daily intake.

This study has shown that average exposure of adults to sodium through consumption of effervescent powders was 53.85%, effervescent granules 34.73% and effervescent tablets 94.11%. The highest exposure to sodium was found in effervescent tablets containing acetylsalicylic acid (400mg) and ascorbic acid (240mg) as active pharmaceutical ingredients: 217.20 % for people aged 18 to 50 years; 250.62 % for people aged 51 to 70 years; 271.50 % for people aged 70 and older.

Because of amount of sodium to which patients are exposed through consumption of effervescent dosage forms, health professionals should make effort to inform patients about potential risks. Also, pharmaceutical industry ought to develop effervescent forms with reduced sodium content.

Keywords: Sodium, Excipients, Effervescent dosage forms, Increased blood pressure

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